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Invasive Weed Optimization Algorithm

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Abstract

Invasive Weed Optimization (IWO) algorithm is inspired by biological growth of weed plants. It is a new derivative free numerical stochastic algorithm based on population. Colonizing behaviour of weed plants is utilized in this algorithm. On survival of fittest theory, more fit plants produce more seeds as compared to less fit plants. But since, there may be a probability that some of the less fit plants may have more important information than the higher fit plants, so in weed colony all plants are given chance to participate in process of reproduction. If plants with lesser fitness produce seeds of high fitness they can survive. This property is utilized as novelty of IWO algorithm.

Keywords Fitness Value, Population, Rank, Optimization, Initialization.

Introduction

Since 1960s significant researches have been done on system simplification. On the basis of easy use, cost effectiveness and reduction of complexity a number of researchers have worked on various techniques. Researchers reduce the complexity of system with preserving its input output performance. With the simplification of higher order complex system, their accuracy and all essential characteristics are almost preserved. To reduce the state space model of the systems in time domain this technique is used. Numerous optimization techniques for simplification of system have been explored, such as; Whale Optimization Algorithm [1,2], Hybrid Stochastic Fractal Search Technique [3], Genetic Algorithm [4], Cuckoo Search Algorithm [5], Routh approximation [6].

Invasive weed Optimization is an evolutionary algorithm based on behaviour of growth and reproduction of weed plants. The algorithm was first invented and implemented by Mehrabian and Lucas. Invasive, fast reproduction and distribution, robustness and self-adaptation to the changes in climate conditions are some interesting characteristics of weed plants. A common belief is "Weeds Always Win". In our cropping systems, local farmers usually disturb their local fields very frequently and leave their resources unused. These unused spaces become an opportunity to weed plants for invading. For the IWO approach, the original model is not necessary to be controllable and observable. Since in reproduction process mating is not required by weeds, new seeds can be generated by each weed independently. By this nature of weeds each agent in the algorithm may have varying number of variables during the process of optimization. In IWO algorithm, one of the optimization parameters can be decided as the number of variables.

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to understand the Invasive Weed Optimization Algorithm.

Review of Literature

Various studies has been done for this research paper which is discussed through out the paper.

Main Text

The steps of the IWO algorithm are as under:

Step 1: The seeds are initialized depending upon the number of selected variables (d) of the given problem, distributed uniformly over the entire solution space.

Step 2: Seed set is created after generating all the selected variables of the given problem randomly within their effective lower and upper limits. Thus, each seed contains random values for each variable in the solution space. Each seed set represents a potential solution of the given problem. Generate several seed set to create a Seed matrix (S) of size $(Pop_{max} \times d)$. The total number of plants in the population is selected as Pop_{max} after satisfying their limits.

Step 3: The fitness value of all individuals of the current seed set (S) (each row (plant) of S) is calculated according to the objective/fitness function considered in the optimization problem. These seeds then evolve into weed plants capable of producing new units.

Step 4: Each individual (plant) is ranked based on its fitness with respect to other weeds. Subsequently, each weed produces new seeds depending on its rank in the whole population in seed set. Starting with the maximum number of seeds (N_{max}) produced by the best fit plant. All plants are participating in reproduction process which adds a new attribute to the optimization providing chances to contribute useful information (good result) by less fit plants during iteration process.

Step 5: The number of seeds to be created by each weed alters linearly from N_{min} to N_{max} which can be computed by:

$$= \frac{F_i - F_{worst}}{F_{best} - F_{worst}} (N_{max} - N_{min}) + N_{min}$$

Number of seeds where, F_i is the fitness of i^{th} weed. F_{worst} and F_{best} denotes the worst and best fitness in weed population. The generated seeds are normally distributed over the field with zero mean and varying

$$\sigma_{iter} = \left(\frac{iter_{max} - iter}{iter_{max}} \right)^n (\sigma_0 - \sigma_f) + \sigma_f$$

where, $iter_{max}$ and $iter$ are the maximum number of iteration cycles assigned by the user and current iteration number, respectively σ_0, σ_f

are the predefined initial and final standard deviations and n is the nonlinear modulation index.

Step 6: When all seeds found their positions over the search area, the new seeds grow to the flowering plants after satisfying all the constraints within their limits and then, they are ranked together with their parents in the seed set matrix. Plants with lower ranking in the colony are eliminated to reach the maximum number of plants in the colony ().

Step 7: Survived plants can produce new seeds based on the ranking in the colony. The fittest individual (plant) is selected from the seed-parent combination of current seed set. If the stopping criterion is satisfied, the iterative process is terminated and the results (gain schedule) are displayed, otherwise go to Step 3 for continuation.

Conclusion

The dispersal structure of IWO is continuous and normally distributed over search space and has a decreasing variance parameter centred on each parent plant. Due to this property, the probability to avoid local minima points is more with IWO algorithm as compared to GA and PSO. The IWO approach can be used to tune the PID controller, to reduce the order of linear time invariant systems with preserving their essential characteristics.

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